

Prooxidant Effect of the Crude Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Ficus odorata* Blanco Merr. in vitro: It's Medical Significance

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Abstract : Alongside with antioxidant, pro-oxidant activity is also observed in phytochemical compounds. In the study, *Ficus odorata*, an endemic medicinal plant in the Philippines, was screened for the potential medical application of its pro-oxidant activity. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of terpenes, glycosides and phenolic acids. The crude extract was found to contain low gallic acid and quercetin equivalence. The TLC chromatogram of the crude extract showed that none of the 7 spots obtained has antioxidant activity nor correspond to gallic acid and quercetin standards. Experiments showed that the crude extract has stimulatory activity towards DPPH radicals, hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radicals, superoxide anions and nitric oxide. Moreover, the extract exhibited a low ferric reducing power. The prooxidant activity was evident in the crude ethanolic leaf extract of *F. odorata*, which may provide a better understanding of the plant's pharmacological importance in the prevention of diseases.

Keywords : *Ficus odorata* Blanco, Free Radicals, Oxidative Stress, Prooxidant, Antioxidant

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